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Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) - RP3

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Acronyms

Academic SEO	Academic Search Engine Optimisation
AGPL	Affero General Public Licence
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association without lucrative purpose
AIUCD	Italian Digital Humanities Association
API	Application Programming Interface
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BPD	Business Plan Development
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CH	Channels
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
CNR	Italian National Research Council
CNR-ILC	Italian National Research Council - Institute for Computational Linguistics
CNRS	French National Centre for Scientific Research
CR	Customer Relation
CS	Cusomer Segments
DABAR	Digital Academic Archives and Repositories
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DEP	Dissemination Expert Packages
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DHd	Digital Humanities in the German-Speaking Countries
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EKT	National Documentation Centre
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
EU-RI	European Research Infrastructures
FAIR principles	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

FTE	full time equivalent
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
HRČAK	Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
IBL PAN	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ICTeSSH	Information and Communications Technology enhanced Social Sciences and Humanities
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KA	Key Activities
KNOW/KC	Know-Center
KP	Key Partners
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KR	Key Resources
LC	Lexical Computing
LIDA	Libraries in the Digital Age
LREC	International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation
M	Month
MEOH	Many Embers One Heat
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MWS	Max Weber Foundation - German Humanities Abroad
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
NPO	Non-Profit Organisation
NURO	Nuromedia GmbH
OAPEN	Online Library and Publication Platform
OK Maps	Open Knowledge Maps
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OPERAS RI	OPERAS Research Infrastructure
OS	Open Source
PDES	Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
PUBMET	Publishing and Metrics
R&D	research and development

RI	research infrastructure
RP	reporting period
RS	Revenue Streams
ScaR	Scalable Recommendation-as-a-service
SIG	Special Interest Group
SME	small and medium sized enterprise
SSH	social sciences and humanities
SSHOC	SSH Open Cluster
SWOT	strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats
T	Task
TBS	Trust Building System
THATCamp	The Humanities and Technology Camp
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
UES	User Engagement Strategy
UNIZD	University of Zadar
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
VP	Value Proposition
WP	Work Package

DRAFT

Publishable Summary

The “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) - RP3” outlines the strategy for the TRIPLE project’s dissemination and exploitation. It is the result of the complementary work done in work package 7 “Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability” and work package 8 “Communication and Dissemination”. The main objectives of the PEDR are:

- To build public awareness of the project.
- To create a user base for the [GoTriple](#) platform.
- To communicate the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project.
- To present a governance model as the foundation for effective collaboration among existing partners and future ones, thereby contributing to the sustainability of the GoTriple platform
- To maximise exploitation opportunities of the project's KERs throughout and beyond its development.

Until February 2023, the PEDR has been a living document with this current, final version being the endpoint. Its structure mainly follows the template suggested in the TRIPLE Grant Agreement (proposal part). It has been updated during the project implementation and tailored to the project’s needs and progress on demand. The PEDR is closely linked to the following other deliverables and reports:

- D1.3 “[Data Management Plan DRAFT](#)” (work package [WP1]–31 March 2020)
- D3.1 “[Report on User Needs](#)” (WP3)–31 May 2020
- D7.1 “[Report on Stakeholder and Opportunity Analysis](#)” (WP7)–30 April 2020
- D7.2 “[Intermediate Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)” (WP7)–30 Sept. 2020
- D8.3 “[Communication Strategy](#)” (WP8)–31 July 2020
- Horizon Results Booster Service: PDES-Module C final report for TRIPLE project¹- 1st February 2022
- D7.3 [Business Model Design and Evaluation Results](#) (WP7– 30 November 2022)
- Horizon Results Booster Service: BPD final report for Triple project² - (WP7 - January 2023)
- Horizon Results Booster Service: PDES-Module A Portfolio Research and Innovation Results Project Group: COS4CLOUD³ - (WP8 - October 2022)
- D7.4 [Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#) (WP7– January 2023)

D8.4 is a combination mainly of D8.4 (Draft), D8.3, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4 and any other reports which will continually provide new inputs until the end of the project.

¹ PDES stands for Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy service provided by Virag Zsar from the European HRB program. The report is confidential but has been sent to the Project Officer.

² BPD stands for Business Plan Development service provided by Virag Zsar from the European HRB program. The report is confidential but has been sent to the Project Officer.

³ The portfolio created by Frederico Drago and Rob Carillo after completing Module A is confidential.

Section 1 of the PEDR outlines key information about the TRIPLE Project (i.e. key messages to communicate, as identified in the deliverable D8.3 "[Communication Strategy](#)"), which is relevant to contextualise the results. Sections 2 and 3 reflect the communication team's ideas for a Plan for the Dissemination of Results and a Plan for the Exploitation of Results, respectively. Section 4 provides an overview of the project's KERs and the GoTriple business model (BM).

The PEDR-RP3 further features the results of analysis and activities being conducted during the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) programme work packages (WP) 7 "Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability" and 8 "Communication and Dissemination" participated in.

Module C "Exploitation Service" of the programme was completed by WP7 between October 2021 and January 2022. The subsequent service "Business Plan Development" ran from April 2022 to September 2022. As mentioned in the list above, a finalized version of the intermediary report from September 2022 is available since January 2023. The Exploitation Strategy Seminars related to that action were held remotely and aimed at strengthening the capacity of the project. Using the project's research results the team sought to enhance and improve the partner's exploitation strategy.

Module A, which together with module B represents the dissemination service of the programme, was completed by WP8 between August 2022 and September 2022. Module B was started in December 2022 and is currently in progress.

1. THE TRIPLE PROJECT

The following sections outline the core messages of the TRIPLE project: some key facts and figures about the project itself and the platform to be developed, goals and impacts as well as results of the project.

1.1. TRIPLE Key Facts and Figures

Some key facts and figures about the **TRIPLE project**:

- TRIPLE is an acronym which stands for **Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration**
- The TRIPLE project is responsible for developing the discovery platform [GoTriple](#)
- Launch: 1 October 2019
- Official kick-off: 4 December 2019
- Project duration: 42 months (2019–2023)
- Financed under the Horizon 2020 framework programme with approx. 5.6 million Euros
- Consortium of 22 partners from 15 European countries
- Coordinated from France by [Huma-Num](#), a unit of the [French National Centre for Scientific Research \(CNRS\)](#)
- Approx. 90 staff members contributing work to one or more of the [eight work packages](#)

Some key facts about [GoTriple](#), the **platform** developed by **TRIPLE**:

- is the heart of the project and was released as a prototype in autumn 2021; since January 2023 the platform is production ready.
- is an innovative multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities (SSH);
- provides a single access point for exploring, finding, accessing and reusing materials such as literature, data, projects and researcher profiles at European scale;
- is the discovery service of the Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities ([OPERAS](#)) [service catalogue](#).

1.2. TRIPLE Goals and Impacts

TRIPLE's main goals and areas of impact represent the project's unique selling point.

The main goals of the TRIPLE project are (Figure 1):

FIGURE 1. MAIN GOALS OF THE TRIPLE PROJECT

- with GoTriple, TRIPLE created a single multilingual access point to SSH material currently scattered across different repositories.
- the discovery platform GoTriple developed by the TRIPLE project helps users to explore, find, access and (re)use open scholarly SSH resources: research data and publications, researcher profiles and projects.

- ❑ TRIPLE makes use of innovative digital tools to support research, and it discovers new ways of funding research, for instance through the OPERAS crowdfunding service.⁴
- ❑ TRIPLE fosters new interdisciplinary collaborations in Europe and worldwide by bringing together researchers with diverse skills, practices and competencies, language and cultural backgrounds.
- ❑ TRIPLE supports scientific, industrial and societal applications of SSH discipline by maximising the reuse of resources through Open Science and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles and a multidisciplinary transfer of knowledge.
- ❑ TRIPLE increases the economic and societal impact of SSH resources for the scientific community at large, but also for citizens, policy makers, the media and enterprises.

The TRIPLE project and GoTriple platform aim to have the following main impacts (Figure 2):

FIGURE 2. MAIN IMPACTS OF THE TRIPLE PROJECT AND GOTRIPLE PLATFORM

⁴ <https://wemakeit.com/channels/operas?locale=en>

- **User-orientation:** The TRIPLE project integrates co-design principles into research and the development of new services. Users have been critical to all phases of the research process, from needs analysis to tool testing and evaluation, as they know best how they work and what they need.
- **Contribution to the objectives of Open Science:** The TRIPLE project improves access to open content and resources and facilitates collaborations across disciplinary and language boundaries. Data sharing and usage according to the FAIR principles is fostered.
- **Integration into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC):** The TRIPLE project worked in close collaboration with the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC) project. Communication efforts were aligned and events were jointly organised.⁵ GoTriple is indexed in the SSH Open Marketplace, which serves as the main interdisciplinary entry point for SSH data and SSH research within the EOSC. Being an interdisciplinary and multilingual hub for various stakeholders, GoTriple also serves as a gateway to the complex EOSC ecosystem.
- **Strong ties between research, industry and society:** GoTriple facilitates more efficient and effective SSH research for society at large by involving civil society, public institutions and companies in scientific projects, thus strengthening the links between different types of stakeholders. Citizens' trust towards the sciences will be strengthened, and the competitiveness and growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) will increase.
- **Reconnection of culture and science:** The GoTriple platform is not only a platform that ensures the discoverability of SSH resources and facilitates collaborations but also a cultural platform to discover, understand and highlight European diversity in terms of societies, languages and practices. It helps to promote cultural diversity in Europe.

1.3. TRIPLE Results

In a guideline by the [European Intellectual Property Rights \(IPR\) Helpdesk](#) project, the term “results” as used in the Horizon 2020 programme project results is defined as follows:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.” (Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

In a nutshell, results encompass all project outcomes that may be used by the project partners or other relevant stakeholders outside the project. They have the potential to be either commercially exploited (e.g. concrete products or

⁵ For an overview see: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/synergies/operas-triple>.

services) or lay the foundation for further research, work or innovations (e.g. novel knowledge, insights, technologies, methods, data).”⁶

According to this definition, various types of “results” of the TRIPLE project have already been produced within the project duration time frame. These include:

- the discovery platform [GoTriple](#) with its innovative services
- the [Multilingual TRIPLE Vocabulary](#)⁷ (KER)
- the [TRIPLE training toolkit](#)⁸, an open workflow to design and deliver online training events following the FAIR-by-design method.
- research results, i.e. results from surveys, qualitative research, interviews, workshops etc.
- deliverables⁹
- scientific publications¹⁰ (individual and joint publications relating to the project)
- other communication materials (e.g. presentations/posters/workshops) relating to the project

2. PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS

The plan for the dissemination of results outlines how TRIPLE stakeholders have been reached and the current strategy of how to reach the TRIPLE stakeholders in the future, i.e. the target audiences and the different European national communities.

TRIPLE has implemented a number of dissemination measures which focused, at first, on the communication of the project and its objectives while, at a later stage, these channels have been used to present and communicate the results of the project, its methodologies and workflows. Following a brochure by the European Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Helpdesk, “dissemination” then means to “transfer knowledge and results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research”.¹¹

⁶ The European IPR Helpdesk (2018). Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.

<https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>, p. 15.

⁷ The Triple Vocabulary is a multilingual and hierarchical set of SSH-related concepts. It is a subset of LCSH (Library of Congress Subject Headings) that cover popular SSH aspects and is enhanced with labels in Greek, French, Polish, German, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish and Croatian. The vocabulary is used for the automatic annotation of the publications hosted in the GoTriple platform (<https://www.gotriple.eu/>). DOI: [10.12681/semantics.gr/SSH-LCSH](https://doi.org/10.12681/semantics.gr/SSH-LCSH).

⁸ TRIPLE Training Toolkit (2022). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6256198](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6256198).

⁹ <https://project.gotriple.eu/deliverables/>

¹⁰ <https://project.gotriple.eu/publications/>

¹¹ The European IPR Helpdesk (2018). Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.

<https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>, p. 13.

All project partners must disseminate the project results and ensure Open Access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. A more detailed description of dissemination measures can be found in D8.3 [“Communication Strategy”](#).

2.1. Target Audiences

It is important to carefully identify target audiences for the platform as this is paramount to the success of most Information and Communications Technology (ICT) projects (not only research platforms and infrastructures) to obtain a deep and qualitative understanding of the end users and to involve them in taking relevant decisions about how an ICT platform and the associated services can support the users’ goals.¹² The design of the GoTriple platform is based on a strong user-centred perspective with the main assumption of working in close contact with end-users, SSH researchers in particular, but also to work with other relevant stakeholders (such as policy makers or SMEs).

Two main differentiating criteria were agreed upon: academic and non-academic stakeholders. Subsequently, five representative stakeholder groups were identified for each main category, including possible subgroups as shown in Figure 3. A list of the different target audiences, along with the relevant dissemination measures that the project will take to inform each audience group, is shown in Table 1 of the deliverable D8.3 [“Communication Strategy”](#) (Section 5.2).

FIGURE 3. TRIPLE STAKEHOLDER OVERVIEW DIVIDED INTO THE CATEGORIES OF “ACADEMIC” AND “NON-ACADEMIC”

¹²Ibid. p. 26.

The stakeholders were classified in the influence-interest matrix depicted in Figure 4. The general management strategies can be described as follows: Stakeholders with high power and low interest shall be kept satisfied. Those with low interest and low power shall be only involved with minimum effort. A stakeholder with low power and high interest in a project shall be kept informed, and finally, the high power, high-interest stakeholders shall be closely involved and informed. For a detailed definition of the four quadrants, see Section 2 of deliverable D7.1 [“Report on Stakeholder and Opportunity Analysis”](#).

FIGURE 4. TRIPLE POWER-INTEREST MATRIX

As researchers are the key stakeholders, the user research undertaken as part of WP3 “Co-Design and User Research” focused on them along with a smaller number of non-academic stakeholders to ensure the needs of the end-users and the huge variety of the working practices that exist in the SSH research community across Europe could fully be understood and met. Clearly, this is not an easy task, due to the huge variety of disciplines and the Europe-wide spread of researchers and also the heterogeneity of research practices and available resources. WP3 was designed to use a mix of social sciences and design research approaches in order to tackle these challenges and then study the TRIPLE users.

User research was conducted during the first phase of the TRIPLE project in the form of interviews. The main output of this research was the production of personas and scenarios. From each scenario created, a list of end-user needs/requirements supported the consequent

design of the platform's end-user interface and constituted the basis for the subsequent co-design activities was obtained. The user needs have also been grouped into emerging functionalities. Deliverable D3.1 "[Report on User Needs](#)" reports on the initial identification of the user needs for TRIPLE and on the personas and scenarios produced. This output was then the basis for codesign work conducted in Tasks 3.2 "Co-design of innovative and new services", 3.3 "Trust-building system user design research" and 3.4 "Data-Driven User Profiles and Dashboard design research" where the user needs were refined and novel design ideas based on these needs were produced, focusing on the platform innovative services (T3.2), the Trust Building System (T3.3) and the platform dashboards (T3.4). The results of the codesign work are reported in the respective deliverables 3.2 "[Report on co-design of User Profiles and Dashboard research](#)", 3.3 "[Report on co-design of Recommendation System Research](#)" and 3.4 "[Report on co-design with users of the innovative services of the TRIPLE platform](#)". Overall, this part of the work allowed designing a platform that responds to the actual user needs of researchers and other stakeholders.

Additional to evaluating and testing the platform and its features, the pool of beta testers that have been assembled by WP3 has been used for dissemination measures: Already working closely with the platform and the TRIPLE team, members of the test pool support WP8 by being part of the ambassador strategy (see below) and disseminating information via their institutions and networks. Likewise, the group of beta testers itself has been continuously supplied with information about events, training, and results of the TRIPLE project.

Metrics enable the consortium to monitor parameters such as user numbers, users' countries of origin, and users' professional groups. This will allow planning and adjusting stakeholder-oriented dissemination activities to tackle any representation imbalances uncovered. Deliverable D7.4 "[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)" reports on the metrics dashboard in more detail.¹³

During the last reporting period, WP8 has begun participating in the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) Program of the European Commission.¹⁴ Forming a project group with [Cos4Cloud](#), [INODE](#), and [CS3MESH4EOSC](#), Module A has been completed in October 2022.¹⁵ Module A includes a stakeholder analysis aiming to identify the most important stakeholders in common for all projects participating in the project group, thereby allowing joint dissemination activities tailored to shared stakeholders (Module B). The following stakeholders have been identified as the most important for the project group: Start-ups and SMEs, policy makers, Funding Agencies including EU & national digital agencies, researchers and academia, civil society, NGO's and Citizens. Module B started in December 2022 and is currently in progress. The two Dissemination Expert Packages (DEP) that have been chosen by the project group are DEP 2: "Collaboration Page" and DEP 3: Joint Brochure/Promotional Factsheet". A short, introductory video presenting the projects in the project group has been released in February.¹⁶

¹³ See section 3.2 "Market Insights" pp. 22-24.

¹⁴ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>.

¹⁵ Drago, Frederico, Carillo, Rob: Portfolio of Research and Innovation Results [confidential].

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OO8Q1qNfWMA>.

2.2. Dissemination Measures

At the beginning of the project, the TRIPLE consortium identified and performed a series of main dissemination measures to support the project outreach. These dissemination measures are public and openly accessible to everyone. They focus first on communicating about the project and its aims, and then on the results and outcomes of TRIPLE, following the project evolution. In the bullet list below, an overview of these measures is provided, while in the subsequent Section 2.3, the dissemination measures are tailored to the various target audiences.

- **TRIPLE events:** Conferences, workshops, trainings, webinars, THATcamps (i.e. an open space format event, a so-called “unconference”¹⁷), book sprints and hackathons organised by the TRIPLE project following the project’s tasks and description of work. These events have been organised throughout the duration of the project and aimed to create a community around TRIPLE serving as an initial user base for GoTriple.
- **National node events:** From October 2022 on, OPERAS’s national nodes started organising workshops with the specific aim to recruit users for GoTriple. In collaboration with OPERAS’s international partners, these workshops aim to involve the national community of each of the research infrastructure’s national nodes.
- **Publications:** Scientific articles on the project, its objectives, workflows and results published in journals mainly dedicated to the SSH research communities, but also in professional channels relevant to service providers, librarians, policy and Open Science officers and other media to increase circulation. Also includes public info materials such as flyers, posters and infographics.
- **Project deliverables:** All project deliverables are being publicly deposited in the OPERAS community on Zenodo for users to openly access them.¹⁸ The deliverables note the progress of the project, the different workflows, methodologies, challenges and solutions for developing the platform.
- **Reports on TRIPLE-initiated events:** All TRIPLE-initiated events are evaluated by the participants of these events to properly measure the impact of the dissemination measures taken.
- **Reports on events that the TRIPLE consortium participates in:** To keep track of the various events at which the TRIPLE project and GoTriple platform are represented by its consortium

¹⁷ “THATCamp stands for ‘The Humanities and Technology Camp’. It is an unconference: an open, inexpensive meeting where humanists and technologists of all skill levels learn and build together in sessions proposed on the spot.” (<https://thatcamp.org/about/index.html>). The name “THATCamp” is trademarked, and the event needs to be registered.

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/>

members, and the potential impact of this participation, reports will be expected from the consortium members on participation in these events, outlining the knowledge exchange and networking opportunities. Events organized by ERICs (DARIAH, CESSDA, CLARIN) and the EOSC have been the focus of this outreach endeavour. By creating synergies among the European projects and infrastructures the TRIPLE team aims to establish GoTriple as a well-known discovery solution. With the platform being one of the project's KERs, increasing its prestige enhances the sustainability of the project.

- **Training and guidelines:** This is an important dissemination measure closer to the development of the TRIPLE platform, including training (virtual or face-to-face) and guidelines for how users can make the best use of the platform for their research (including infographics). To further ensure the future use and sustainability of GoTriple, WP6 “Open Science and EOSC Integration” has created the [TRIPLE Training Toolkit](#) helping users to find the training most suited to their needs. Additionally, a four-episode series of Video Tutorials has been created that is available via the TRIPLE YouTube Channel and on Zenodo.¹⁹
- **Advocacy material:** As Open Science lies close to the heart of the project, advocacy material on Open Access and Open Science has been prepared by the project, explaining the wider environment of the EOSC and its relation with TRIPLE. This includes TRIPLE Deliverables D6.1 “[Report on the General Interoperability Requirements](#)”, “D6.5 “[Report on Open Science within the EOSC](#)” and the KER “[TRIPLE Training Toolkit](#)”, Additionally, as featured in D7.4 “[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)”, a position paper by the TRIPLE consortium “Contributing to EOSC: Concrete Needs and Open Questions” has been released.²⁰

More detailed information on dissemination measures, including a Dissemination Measures/Target Audience Matrix, as well as on different communication channels (website, social media channels, newsletter, list of mailing lists and newsletters, the OPERAS Zenodo repository and face-to-face communication) can be found in deliverable D8.3 “[Communication Strategy](#)”.

2.3. User Engagement Strategy

In the third and final reporting period of the project, we launched a User Engagement Strategy (UES) that specifically aims to recruit registered users. The UES, which is led by WP1 “Management” and organized collaboratively with WP8, draws from all of the above-mentioned dissemination measures and heavily focuses on engaging with (potential) users. The UES aims primarily to fulfil two targets: 1) To motivate potential users to engage and register at GoTriple,

¹⁹ YouTube Playlist: TRIPLE Video Tutorials: <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL2UW3hSUQBFOzNo8H8nDRivURieOQQ5nl>; on Zenodo, the videos are available via the OPERAS community.

²⁰ See section 4 of the Deliverable, p. 41ff.

and 2) to create sustainable dissemination material that can be used as a guideline on how to use the platform beyond the end of the project.

Measures to reach target 1) include the recruitment of [TRIPLE ambassadors](#) to engage with social media posts and promote GoTriple at events as well as the organization of a series of hands-on workshops organized by the OPERAS national nodes. So far, workshops in French, Portuguese, Polish, Greek and German have been held. The workshops will continue to be organized beyond the lifespan of the TRIPLE project.

To fulfil target 2), the TRIPLE team has taken part in the [CESSDA Podcast](#). In an interview with TRIPLE team members and one TRIPLE ambassador as a user representative, features of the platform are introduced and discussed for further dissemination. Additionally, in collaboration with mentioned ambassadors, a four-episode series of Video Tutorials has been created. Each of the videos produced focuses on different aspects of the platform: Multilingualism, discovery, onboarding/registration and public profile settings. The videos were created to serve two purposes simultaneously: Raise interest in key features of the platform, thereby serving as promotional material, and, simultaneously, provide tutorials on how to use the platform.

Furthermore, at the consortium meeting in September 2022, a workshop has been held to create a toolkit for slogans and taglines tailored to each of the stakeholders. All partners can draw from this toolkit. On its basis, visual material available to the consortium has been created to complement D8.2 "[Communication Toolkit](#)".

To keep dissemination activities going after the end of the project the TRIPLE team has initiated chosen dissemination measures that will be carried out beyond the end of the project in March 2023:

- The dissemination of information concerning GoTriple will be operated by OPERAS after the TRIPLE project has ended.
- The OPERAS national nodes will continue to disseminate information about GoTriple within their national communities, with the GoTriple onboarding workshops organised by them continuing after the TRIPLE project has ended.
- GoTriple is part of the OPERAS Services portfolio, and as such acts as an important part of the OPERAS communication strategy, including presentations, publications, social media presence and marketing actions.
- GoTriple will be included in the marketing activities of the OPERAS RI.
- The TRIPLE project aims to establish collaborations not only with individuals but also with institutions and journals to create a sustainable form of ambassadorship that will be continued and coordinated by OPERAS from April 2023 on.
- Informational material ([Fact Sheets in nine languages](#), [TRIPLE Key Takeaway Brochure](#)) has been created for the purpose of dissemination after the end of the TRIPLE project.

2.4. Dissemination of Project Results by Partners

The TRIPLE consortium consists of a network of partners with long expertise in the SSH field. It is therefore strategic for the dissemination success of the project to leverage partners'

individual contacts and related networks to multiply the effect of the outreach activities at geographical, qualitative and quantitative levels. TRIPLE project partners have defined their individual dissemination measures in line with the overall project dissemination strategy. Table 1 provides an overview of how each partner plans to support the dissemination of project results in terms of a) the organisation's/institution's specific target audience, b) main measures and access channels to the identified audiences, c) the contribution of the organisation to the management and implementation of the dissemination process and c) time planning of the dissemination during the project lifespan.

TABLE 1. TRIPLE PROJECT PARTNER/DISSEMINATION MEASURES MATRIX (FEBRUARY 2023)

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
Abertay University	Academic audience; policy makers; SME's; journalists; other interested stakeholders	Academic journals; conference proceedings; Abertay University website; project website; social media	Collaboration with TRIPLE colleagues; participation in the joint writing up of relevant material for dissemination	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan and thereafter; dissemination of initial findings at specific events
CESSDA ERIC	SSH researchers and research institutions; national Service providers; libraries; SSHOC project consortium	Website; service providers' websites; social media channels; annual report; CESSDA ERIC and SSHOC mailing lists; CESSDA events and webinars (IASSIST 22); DDI community, CESSDA Newsletter	Active participation in WP8 activities and promoting project results via CESSDA ERIC communication channels	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan
CLARIN ERIC	SSH community; research infrastructures	Website; social media; training material; face-to-face events	To be specified by the WP for dissemination	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan (website and social media)
CNR (Italy)	Researchers from SSH and other disciplines	CNR-ILC website; CLARIN-IT website and social media (Twitter, Facebook); Italian Open Science Portal; mailing lists (CLARIN-IT Members, AIUCD-L, FLReNet Subscribers, ILC News); external events	Spreading the project progress and results in major events of the sector (LREC Biennial Conference 2020, European Researchers' Night 2020; CLARIN Annual Conference 2021, AIUCD Annual Conference 2021, CLARIN	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
			Bazaar 2021, Open Science Fair 2021, GARR Conference 2022), collaboration with relevant stakeholders to promote and disseminate project activities and results (TRIPLE activities and events featured on the Open Science Portal and shared on social media, TRIPLE training resources hosted on the DARIAH-Campus platform)	
CNRS	French SSH researchers and engineers	Social media; mailing lists; specific events, EOSC and international events via the main coordinator of the project who is also one of the directors of the EOSC association, OPERAS events	CNRS is the OPERAS French national node. CNRS is contributing to TRIPLE scientific publications via the main coordinator of the project. Several French workshops have been led via Huma-Num and OpenEdition to present the platform to the French scientific community	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan and beyond the project to ensure the development and sustainability of the platform. CNRS will be involved in the governance and maintenance of the servers.
DARIAH ERIC	Research communities (Arts & (Digital) Humanities); policy makers; Open Science stakeholders; research infrastructures; project partners (SSH)	Website; mailing list; monthly newsletters; social media (Twitter, LinkedIn); Members channels (websites, mailing lists, social media); Project partners channels (websites, mailing lists, social media); Training materials; Events	Active participation in the dissemination activities and user engagement strategy under the coordination of WP8; provision of content for the TRIPLE website when requested, dissemination of the project updates through DARIAH's channels	Ongoing since the beginning of the project, following main project outputs and actively contributing to the user engagement strategy during the last year of the project.

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
		(DARIAH events, TRIPLE events, external events); conferences		
EGI	EGI researchers in SSH area; policy makers; SMEs; developers	Newsletter; booklet; conferences; mailing list; social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Blog); community forum	Presentation of TRIPLE results in EGI conferences; newsletter issues to introduce TRIPLE and its services; joint organisation of workshops/events; communication of TRIPLE news via EGI social media	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan; article about TRIPLE in EGI newsletter in 4th quarter of 2020; EGI conference Nov. 2020, EGI Conference Oct 2021, EGI Conference Oct 2022
IBL PAN	Researchers from SSH and other disciplines; service providers, e.g. libraries, scientific publishers; public authorities; policy makers	Mailing lists; social media; "Polish Studies Newsletter" website; IBL PAN website; OPERAS-PL website; Digital Humanities Center newsletter; project deliverables; reports; advocacy materials; TRIPLE, IBL PAN and external events	Translation of materials into Polish; sharing information via mailing lists, social media channels, newsletter and institutional websites (IBL PAN and OPERAS-PL)	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan
Know-Center	Scientific communities in the areas of computational social science, Open Science and recommender systems (WP4 "Integration and Building of TRIPLE Platform & WP5 "Development of Innovative Services"), innovation	Social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn); website; deliverables; scientific publications; KC summer academy 2020 (online sessions to ScaR and business modelling)	Distributing information through different channels; collaborative work on TRIPLE publications	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
	management & business model innovation (WP7); Open Science communities and other researchers; data-driven business that benefits from recommender systems or innovative business modelling			
Lexical Computing	Corpus linguists; translators; terminologists; marketing and branding specialists; SEO specialists; NLP, NLU & AI specialists	Website; social media channels; mailing lists; publications	Dissemination related activities on website and social media, presenting TRIPLE as part of our other presentations and networking activities	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan; social media and mailing list communication can be published at TRIPLE's request
MEOH	All individuals and all stakeholders	Trust Building System (TBS) - word of mouth; company website; TRIPLE website and related events	Through personal newsfeed in the TBS; through website; mailing list; online events; social media	Mostly once the TBS codesign workshop and their technical implementation have happened, i.e. roughly around M30
MWS	Researchers (esp. history, art history, sociology) in MWS's institutes worldwide, with a focus on German researchers, German DH community, German governmental representatives and	MWS website and social media channels (Twitter); MWS blogs, newsletter, printed magazine; OPERAS and TRIPLE websites and social media channels (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn); attendance at relevant conferences (e.g. annual DhD conference); UES	MWS-internal public relations department; WP8 leadership's regular work; connection with OPERAS RI communication; management of OPERAS communication	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
	policy makers on federal and regional levels			
National Documentation Centre (EKT)	Greek SSH researchers; librarians; publishers; policy makers; funders	Website; social media; mailing lists; external events; advocacy material; training material; conferences	Distribution of information through different channels (mailing lists, social media channels, etc.); participation in the writing of relevant material for dissemination; translation of relevant material into Greek	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan
Net7	SSH academics; possibly other audiences such as academic audience from other domains, policy makers and public authorities.	Direct mailing to company's direct contact in the field; relevant networks where Net7 is involved (e.g GO FAIR); specific newsletters/ mailing lists; SSH related conferences. Secondary target audience: direct email (e.g. in case of local public authorities); Net7 general communication channels (e.g. corporate social media, website)	Active participation under the coordination of the WP8 leader; provision of content for dissemination including writing scientific articles and papers; sharing project updates through the company's social media channels; sharing updates with relevant Net7 customers that could be interested in the project outputs	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan and in conjunction with relevant scientific events; in line with project's main output delivery
Nuromedia	Research communities; public authorities and enterprises	External events; trade shows	Dissemination of the project and project progress at trade shows	-
OAPEN	Researchers from SSH and other disciplines; service providers such as	OAPEN and DOAB channels: websites, mailing lists, blog, social media, OAPEN toolkit	Sharing information through OAPEN dissemination channels	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan and after project close

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
	libraries or scientific publishers; public authorities and policy makers			
Open Knowledge Maps	Researchers; students; librarians, educators; science journalists; practitioners; stakeholders (e.g. libraries, repositories, funding organisations, publishers)	Website; newsletter; social media (e.g. Twitter, Facebook); github; webinars (usually hosted by third parties such as COAR or Wikimedia); mailing lists; conferences and other events; participation in networks (e.g. GO FAIR, citizen-science.at); training materials (e.g. presentations slides, workshop concepts that can also be run autonomously)	Contributing to papers and posters; presenting TRIPLE as part of other presentations and networking activities; dissemination of TRIPLE-related activities via mailing lists and social media accounts	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan
Universidade de Coimbra	Research communities (Arts & Digital Humanities); policy makers; Open Science stakeholders; research infrastructures and project partners (particularly in the area of SSH)	TRIPLE website; social media; mailing lists; OPERAS events; publications; reports; project deliverables; external events; advocacy materials; training services and guiding materials	Active participation in the dissemination activities; promotion of meetings/training on specific topics; co-authoring presentations, papers and reports	Started in July 2019; continuously throughout the project's lifespan (see e.g. the website " UC Open Science " and related social media - Twitter , Instagram , Facebook)

Partner	Organisation's specific target audience(s)	Main measures and access channels to the identified target audience(s)	Contribution of the organisation to the TRIPLE dissemination process	Period of dissemination measures
UNIZD	Croatian SSH community; publishers; institutional and national service providers; libraries; citizens	Institutional and national mailing lists (researchers, librarians, publishers, journals, OS); social networks (institutional); national OS portal (otvorena-znanost.hr); national and international conferences, summer schools organised by UNIZD (PUBMET, LIDA...); webinars; workshops; face-to-face and online events with aim of popularisation of scholarly communications topics - Quarter to Noon for Scholarly Communication program [Podne manje kvarat]; training materials	Dissemination of information through different channels; participation in research projects and publications; promotion of Open Science practices in general; other dissemination models defined by WP8	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan
OPERAS AISBL	European SSH community; publishers; libraries; research infrastructures; universities	Institutional and European mailing lists (researchers, librarians, publishers, journals, OS); social networks (institutional); European conferences, webinars; workshops; face-to-face events; training materials	Dissemination via the national nodes and OPERAS newsletter	Continuously throughout the project's lifespan and beyond as the discovery platform is a service of OPERAS AISBL
FoxCub	SME, private data agency	French network		Continuously throughout the project's lifespan

2.5. Dissemination Management

Work package 8 is responsible for the communication and dissemination of results and is supported by all TRIPLE partners.

Dissemination feedback and evaluation: To align the dissemination activities, communication channels and key messages, communication and dissemination activities have been regularly reviewed. Until February 2023, the TRIPLE consortium has participated and presented the TRIPLE project and/or GoTriple at 103 external events. The project itself has organized 64 events, 50 of which have been open to the public. After each event, an evaluation form has been circulated among the participants. Following the visit to external events, consortium members fill out a report to measure the outreach activity in terms of event attendance etc. Thereby, a continuous feedback loop for outreach activities has been established, allowing swift adaptations if needed. The project management team and the communication officer meet regularly to discuss opportunities, strengths and weaknesses of the dissemination process. These regular meetings allow aligning the dissemination strategy accordingly until the very end of the project.

Success indicators (Key Performance Indicators [KPIs]) have been used to measure the effect of dissemination strategies and evaluate the success of communication activities. The KPIs depended on the dissemination activity and the phase of the project. For example, KPIs for social media dissemination include the number of followers, impressions and interactions. In the case of oral communication channels, like a workshop, KPIs were, among others, the number of participants at the event, their feedback, and their participation in future events. For the remaining time of the project and beyond, dissemination activities, especially social media dissemination activities, focus heavier on user engagement than in the first stages of the project, meaning KPIs most important for evaluation are “engagements”, “engagement rates” (social media) and the number of users (GoTriple platform) in comparison to “impressions”, for example. As of February 2023 the project’s Twitter account has 867 followers. The measures taken as part of the UES were followed by a significant increase in engagement rates on Twitter. In comparison to the months before in reporting period 3, from November 2022 the post engagement rate has increased by 63,9%.²¹

As of January 2023 GoTriple is no longer in beta mode. The platform’s success and sustainability are thereby dependent on its users and how they engage with the platform. To measure the users’ behaviour on the platform itself a dashboard is being created to gather information on the indicators such as gender, age and language used by GoTriple users. Because this data is set to display potential imbalances (e.g. a predominance of male users) in the user base of the platform, gathering this data will not only allow the team to evaluate its dissemination effort

²¹ This number has been acquired via [Hootsuite](#) Analytics.

but to take corrective actions as well, thereby serving as “compass indicators”.²² This will also ensure that GoTriple contributes to better inclusivity, diversity and equality, in line with its Open Science objectives. As these compass indicators display imbalances that would otherwise go unnoticed they allow a quick adjustment of dissemination activities. These compass indicators will guide the dissemination of results as they make the social groups that need special attention evident.

Internal coordination: As the dissemination activities will facilitate both the building of a community of users and the entry into the market, it is necessary to keep up the strong internal organisation of the consortium. Most of the tasks have been led by WP8. WP8 has worked closely with WP1 “Management”, WP3 “Co-design and user research” and WP7 “Innovation, exploitation and sustainability”. To assure the quality of dissemination activities, a knowledge and protection management has been constituted at the very beginning of the project.²³

Internal communication follows two main objectives: ensuring the same level of information within the consortium and optimizing reactivity and access to common documents. To achieve both objectives a series of communication tools and regulations have been established which are described in more detail in the confidential deliverable D1.2 “Rules and Procedures Including Monitoring and Evaluation Processes related to TRIPLE Consortium”, especially in section IV.A “Internal communication”.

The knowledge and protection management is organized in five value streams:

- Skills (metric examples: fit with future needs, team compositions)
- Networks and relations (stability of networks, quality and quantity of relationships)
- Processes, infrastructure and organisation (efficiency and quality)
- Products, services and integrated systems (research and development [R&D] strategy, quality of products and services)
- Intellectual property rights, Open Access and data management (those aspects are developed in the Exploitation plan part below).

The PCT (Project Coordination Team) composed of the coordinator (WP1) and communication officer (WP8) launched a survey to collect the expertise of each partner of the consortium to give out tasks to appropriate people, and involve skilled colleagues who were not initially devoted to the spoken tasks. This approach has also proved beneficial in crossing skills and getting partners to work together. On a yearly basis and during the pandemic, the coordinator

²² de Paoli, Stefano, Blotière, Emilie, Forbes, Paula & Arasteh-Roodsary, Sona Lisa (2022): Measuring and Promoting the Success of an Open Science Discovery Platform through “Compass Indicators”: The GoTriple Case. In: Publications, 10 (4), 49. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications10040049>.

²³ The responsibilities allocated within the consortium have been described and defined in TRIPLE Deliverable D1.4 “Risk and Quality Management Plan” (confidential).

launched an internal questionnaire to the consortium to collect possible coordination needs and the level of satisfaction with the management of the project, both at the administrative and technical level.

3. PLAN FOR EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

Exploitation is recognised as one of the key enablers for the success of the TRIPLE project. Hence all partners within the project are aware of and committed to the exploitation of the project results, and the proposed focus of the project research and development (R&D) strongly adheres to their research and business strategies. The consortium, with its diverse and complementary research and business contexts and capabilities, provides all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring TRIPLE results to all targeted user communities.

In general terms, the exploitation strategy depends on the actual exploitable assets. The exploitation strategy of the TRIPLE project followed a stepwise approach and was based on the combination of a bouquet of activities conducted throughout the project duration. It varied in intensity based on the amount of information that was available and the produced results during the project's lifetime. In addition, different exploitable assets were exploited by different stakeholders based on the management of intellectual property rights (IPR).

Exploitation Models: The TRIPLE consortium recognises three main exploitation models for the project results: 1) The **commercial exploitation model**, which implies the partly paid provision of the project results to specific customer segments, complying with a pricing scheme which will be defined in the TRIPLE business plan, 2) The **research exploitation model**, which implies the re-utilisation of the research know-how acquired in future research activities, and 3) The **technological exploitation model**, which implies the re-utilisation of the technological know-how acquired for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them. However, not all project partners and interested stakeholders may exploit all project results using the three models defined above. The exploitation models of the TRIPLE project results will be dependent upon three main parameters: a) the nature and interests of the project partners and stakeholders in general, b) the distribution model (commercial or non-commercial) of the project results, and c) the distribution of the IPRs amongst the project partners.

The exploitation model 1 (commercial) will be further elaborated in the subsequent Section 3.1. Model 2 (research) and 3 (technological) are further specified in Section 3.2.

3.1. Joint Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy of TRIPLE is based upon the “Innovation Management for Practitioners – How to Convert Research into Commercial Success Story” report,²⁴ issued by the European Commission aiming to tackle the European Paradox, namely a strong science base yet weak innovation performance, and has been tailored to the specificities, needs and results of the

²⁴ European Commission (2013). Innovation-How to Convert Research into Commercial Success Story. https://ec.europa.eu/research/industrial_technologies/pdf/how-to-convert-research-into-commercial-story_en.pdf.

project. Throughout the tailoring process, the consortium paid special attention to the identified impact factors for market-oriented exploitation, and integrated them into its overall strategy, from setting up the consortium to support future commercialisation, to performing a profound market analysis to identify the market targeted and the strength of the market demand. The WP7 team worked intensively on the design and evaluation of a suitable business model to ensure the economic sustainability of the discovery platform.

To reach this, a reliable Governance Model was developed. The TRIPLE Governance framework named “GoTriple Committee” defines responsibilities and practices, policies, and procedures used to set strategic direction, achieve objectives, manage risks, and allocate resources. The current status of the TRIPLE Governance Model (see Figure 5) consists of the GoTriple Committee with 2 subgroups (User Engagement Subgroup and Data & Tool Subgroup), a Change Advisory Board (CAB) and includes the collaboration with OPERAS in its role as future operator of GoTriple. This collaboration is ensured by the involvement of a GoTriple representative in the OPERAS Service and Technology Board (STB), which manages the overall OPERAS service portfolio.

FIGURE 5. GO TRIPLE GOVERNANCE MODEL

Furthermore, the project consortium agreed on a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), which acts as a framework for cooperation between the Partners regarding the establishment, governance, and operation of the GoTriple Committee. It covers topics such as Partners’ Rights and Expected Contributions, Voting procedures, Acceptance, Withdrawal and Removal of

Partners, Entry in Force and Termination, Resolution of Conflicts, and a description of roles and responsibilities.

3.2. Results of the Joint Exploitation Survey 2023

In order to update and evaluate the goals stated in the draft PEDR in 2020, a follow-up survey to get up-to-date data was conducted. The aim of this survey was to collect information about the willingness of the project partners to participate in the activities of the GoTriple Committee after the funding period of Triple. This survey will help plan governance activities for the GoTriple committee. The following questions (displayed in *italic*) were asked in this survey, the results of each are shown in orange, n=14 partners participated in the survey.

- *Is your institution willing to support the sustainability of the GoTriple platform and thus become a member of the GoTriple Committee after the funding period?* Figure 6 shows the results of this question.

FIGURE 6: DESCRIPTIVES OF ANSWERS TO THE FIRST QUESTION OF THE CONTRIBUTION SURVEY.

TRIPLE has 22 partners, of which n=14 completed the survey, n=11 of these 14 TRIPLE partners are willing to continue to support the GoTriple platform (see Figure 6) in different roles and with different contributions. All the partners who want to continue contributing to GoTriple answered that they will participate in one or more of the following activity categories.

Topics & Activities

- To which of the following main topics would your institution like to contribute?

- Governance** (7 partners want to contribute)
 - To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Governance (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?
 - steering the direction of the GoTriple Committee (6 partners)
 - planning meetings (0 partners)
 - writing minutes (1 partner)
 - approving and defining tasks for subgroups (5 partners)
 - onboarding new committee members (3 partners)
 - Other: Exploring funding opportunities (1 partner)
- User engagement** (7 partners want to contribute)
 - To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. User engagement (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?
 - reviewing user surveys (4 partners)
 - reaching out to new users (4 partners)
 - monitoring user metrics (dashboard) (3 partners)
 - Other: Testing (1 partner)
- Data** (4 partners want to contribute)
 - To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Data (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?
 - ensuring the quality of data sources (2 partners)
 - expanding data sources (1 partner)
 - developing data-related functionalities (1 partner)
 - other general data-related activities (3 partners)
 - Other: support maintaining vocabulary (1 partner)
- Technical consultancy and support** (5 partners want to contribute)
 - To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Technical consultancy and support (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?
 - supporting the change advisory board (2 partners)
 - contributing to technical developments (3 partners)
 - Other: Interface evaluation (1 partner)
- Service component provider** (5 partners want to contribute)

- To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Service component provider (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?*
 - providing a technical service component part of the GoTriple platform (3 partners)*
 - Other: Willing to explore funding to become a service component provider; Non-technical service component (1 partner each)*
- To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Communications and dissemination (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?*
 - planning events (4 partners)*
 - supporting general marketing activities (marketing campaigns) (5 partners)*
 - Other: Training; Presenting GoTriple (talks, publications) (1 partner each)*
- To which activities would your institution contribute w.r.t. Business support (if possible, please already provide a name of a person who can do this activity in the comment field next to the activity)?*
 - monitoring membership activities (income & how many) (2 partners)*
 - monitoring donation activities (income & how many) (2 partners)*
 - support tailored marketing activities for donations and memberships (1 partner)*
 - recruiting new members (1 partner)*
 - evolving (new) business models (3 partners)*
 - scouting project funding (2 partners)*
 - other:*
- Other: Open science (1 partner wants to contribute)*

How many in-kind person months per year would your institution contribute for all the activities in total? $M=1.256$, $SD=0.699$ person months

Most partners who answered the survey want to contribute to GoTriple as GoTriple committee members after the funding period. Furthermore, volunteers were found for almost all activities that were defined as essential. One exception is the "planning meetings" activity in the **governance** category, for which no partner has yet been found. However, not all TRIPLE partners filled out the survey within the time D8.4 "PEDR-RP3" had been written.

3.3. Individual Exploitation Strategies

The main purpose of the individual exploitation plan is to ensure, for each partner, the effective use of project results. The foundation for individual exploitation is the diverse and complementary research and business contexts and capabilities of the consortium partners and their willingness to make available TRIPLE's project results to all targeted user communities. To concretise and update these ambitions a survey with the following questions was administered:

- How would you prioritise your exploitation ambitions (e.g. scientific, business, technical progress, knowledge gain, visibility, image/reputation etc.)? Please rank and start with the most important one.
- What concrete (if possible measurable) results do you expect for your organisation? What gains/benefits do you expect?

FIGURE 7. Individual Exploitation Ambitions of Project Partners

The results of the first question are presented in Figure 7. Universities and research institutions have a main focus of scientific exploitation. Non-profit organisations (NPO) and small and

medium enterprises (SME) plan to exploit the TRIPLE results to support their businesses. European Research Infrastructure Consortiums (ERICs) have a more balanced ratio between business and scientific exploitation ambitions.

Table 2 shows in detail the current status/plan of the individual exploitation ambitions of each consortium partner. This wide range of expected benefits and results forms a solid basis for the effective exploitation of TRIPLE's project results.

TABLE 2. Individual Exploitation Survey Results (status February 2023)

Partner	Partner Type	Prioritisation of exploitation ambition	Concrete expected benefits/results
Abertay University	Public Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Reputation 3. Knowledge gain 4. Visibility 	As an academic/research partner Abertay sees the main exploitation of the project results in terms of scientific publications and in the increased research reputation that derives from participation in a large European project. Publications obtained from the research will facilitate the University's future successful applications for research grants in the areas of co-design and user research.
CESSDA	ERIC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visibility 2. Technical compatibility 	CESSDA and its national Service Providers will benefit from the alignment of metadata and the inclusion of CESSDA in the future. The TRIPLE platform will increase the re-use of its data holdings.
CLARIN	ERIC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Technical progress 3. Visibility 4. Knowledge gain 	TRIPLE's discovery services that link together research data, documents, people and projects will be of benefit to the CLARIN infrastructure, as the outcome of the project will create an additional layer of interaction and collaboration with the broader community. Moreover, the integration of TRIPLE in EOSC will increase the visibility of the CLARIN infrastructure in the wider European ecosystem of SSH and Open Science.
CNR (Italy)	Public Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Technical progress 3. Knowledge gain 4. Visibility 5. Image 6. Business 	CNR will exploit the TRIPLE discovery platform to complement its features with the features and services offered by the CLARIN-IT national node and the CLARIN infrastructure, at large. TRIPLE, indeed, will allow not only to discover research data but also to connect projects and people, thus allowing people to engage and interact. TRIPLE is also expected to facilitate integration into the EOSC and implementation of services in the EOSC marketplace.
CNRS	Public Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Knowledge gain 3. Technical progress 4. Business 5. Image/reputation 	CNRS will exploit TRIPLE platform at two levels: 1. As a pilot to implement new features to the French national platform ISIDORE, 2. To extend the OPERAS services portfolio as planned in the OPERAS-D project. TRIPLE will then be one of the core services OPERAS will offer to the research community at the European level which, in return, will engage more stakeholders with the OPERAS infrastructure.

Partner	Partner Type	Prioritisation of exploitation ambition	Concrete expected benefits/results
DARIAH	ERIC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Knowledge gain 3. Visibility 4. Reputation 	Deepen and expand relations with the other partners involved in the project. Draw inspiration from the deliverables to continue building DARIAH's tools & services. Make sure that the currently developed SSH Open Marketplace and TRIPLE are compatible and complementary. Promote further Open Science in SSH communities. Offer visibility for DARIAH's projects and communities.
EGI	Foundation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical progress 2. Science 3. Business 4. Visibility 	TRIPLE services will be integrated with the EGI Check-in. EGI will support making the TRIPLE services optimally visible in the EOSC portal and marketplace, providing access to a marketplace for data intensive research services that aim at reaching tens of millions of data analysis experts in Europe in the near to medium term future.
IBL PAN	Public Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Technical progress 3. Knowledge gain 	Increasing discoverability and usage of Polish language resources (mapping providers from PL); IBL PAN will have easier and faster access to materials and information in their fields of expertise in different languages.
Know-Center	Research Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Knowledge gain 3. Visibility 4. Reputation 	KC will leverage the work from TRIPLE in order to further develop its recommendation framework ScaR. Furthermore, KC will strengthen its knowledge base in the area of data-driven business models.
Lexical Computing	SME	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Business 2. Technical progress 	LCC will benefit from the alignments between the different thesauri at a European level and from other language data sets created within the project. LC will use the data for further research, to strengthen its Sketch Engine machine and to increase its offers.
MEOH	Non-profit organisation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reputation 2. Business 3. Visibility 4. Knowledge gain 5. Technical progress 	MEOH will further exploit the results of the trust building system for B2B and B2C applications. Additional layers and plug-ins will be considered to support B2C solutions such as scouting for reliable partners and talents beyond the known trusted horizon, disseminating services and ideas, and enabling collective decision making at scale.
MWS	Public Institution/ Foundation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visibility 2. Knowledge gain 3. Scientific 	Growing commitment of MWS institutes to OPERAS and other European research infrastructures, thus fostering the role of MWS as national contact point
National Documentation Centre (EKT)	Public Institution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Knowledge gain 2. Scientific 3. Business 4. Technical 	The main benefits for EKT will be the following: improvement of the portal OpenArchives.gr which is the main provider of Greek content for the TRIPLE platform. Increased discoverability and usage of Greek Open Access content (EKT is the main provider of such content).

Partner	Partner Type	Prioritisation of exploitation ambition	Concrete expected benefits/results
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> progress 5. Image/visibility 	
Net7	SME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Business 2. Knowledge gain 3. Technical progress 4. Reputation 5. Visibility 	Net7 will develop a business plan and deploy its service Pundit into the EOSC marketplace as well as into external markets. Pundit has been released as Open Source (under AGPL 3.0) to foster use and customisation in distinct domains and settings. In terms of segmentation, we plan to address the following main classes of target users: 1) Scholars/researchers, 2) Students/teachers
Nuromedia	SME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Business 2. Technical progress 	Nuromedia plans to exploit the results of the TRIPLE project and the applications and methodologies. Key NURO personnel are doing a lot of sales activities participating in lots of matchmaking events, conferences, workshops and trade shows, where they will promote and disseminate the project and the results with the aim to also generate interest in the further exploitation of TRIPLE, starting with the very beginning of the project. NURO will extend its client base using the knowledge gained during the project.
OAPEN	Non-profit organisation / Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visibility 2. Technical compatibility 	OAPEN will leverage the TRIPLE discovery platform to increase discovery and usage of its Open Access monographs collection, thereby increasing the impact of OA models for monographs. In addition, TRIPLE will improve integration with EOSC.
Open Knowledge Maps	Non-profit organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical progress 2. Visibility 3. Knowledge gain 4. Scientific 5. Business 6. Image 	OKMAPS will use the results from TRIPLE to further develop its visualisation framework Head Start. OKMAPS will also enhance its discovery services with innovative technologies developed in TRIPLE and deploy these services on the Open Knowledge Maps website, on the Custom Services platform (hosted cloud solution), and in the EOSC marketplace. In addition, OKMAPS will refine its own business model based on the outcomes of TRIPLE.
Universidade de Coimbra	Public Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. scientific 2. knowledge gain 3. technical progress 4. visibility 5. reputation 6. business 	Coimbra University (through the digital ecosystem UC Digitalis) will exploit the TRIPLE discovery platform to enhance the visibility of its contents and compliance with FAIR principles. It will as well strongly facilitate the integration in the EOSC and the market place, particularly in the area of SSH.
UNIZD	Public Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scientific 2. Knowledge gain 3. Visibility 4. Image/reputation 	UNIZD will leverage the TRIPLE platform to increase the discovery and usage of Croatian Open Access publications (journals, monographs and others) and research data promoting higher publishing standards and integration with EOSC. Furthermore, sharing different practices and knowledge of TRIPLE partners could

Partner	Partner Type	Prioritisation of exploitation ambition	Concrete expected benefits/results
		5. Technical progress	foster improvements of the services provided by UNIZD (e.g. MorePress publishing platform) and national OS infrastructure (HRČAK, DABAR).
OPERAS AISBL	Non-profit organisation	1. Scientific 2. Knowledge gain 3. Technical progress 4. Visibility 5. Image/reputation 6. Business	OPERAS will be the main exploitation of GoTriple as it has been onboarded within its service portfolio, moreover, the OPERAS AISBL provides a legal and administrative framework; coordination and support; dissemination, communication, and marketing; coordination of service management; community engagement; along with business model development and project funding scouting and coordination. Ultimately, OPERAS will ensure that GoTriple not only persists, but will continue to evolve beyond the life of the project.
FoxCub	SME	1. Business 2. Technical progress 3. Visibility 4. Reputation	Foxcub will exploit the results of the Triple project as well as user feedback to improve the configuration and quality of the components developed for GoTriple: continuous improvement of the automatic classification of documents, progressive alignment of the annotation service with the contents of the Triple vocabulary and optimization of the parameters applied to a project from the field of SSH

3.4. Exploitation Management

In general, TRIPLE exploitation needs to be well coordinated with OPERAS' strategy, since TRIPLE will be a managed service of OPERAS. To ensure economic sustainability for GoTriple as well as the coordination with OPERAS, a reliable Governance Model (see section 3.1) has been developed. This governance model has been developed in detail within the last 2 years and an interim status was reported in deliverable [D7.3 "Business Model Design and Evaluation"](#). The final status can be found in D7.4 "[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)".

Exploitation strategy: The strategy comprised a range of exploitation activities which include:

1. The identification of the innovative exploitable assets, which the project delivered through its results to its target users.
2. The conduction of a thorough market analysis (initial analysis is already reported in deliverable D7.1 "[Report on Stakeholder and Opportunity Analysis](#)") which aimed at the identification of the market towards which TRIPLE is targeted, its segmentation, the positioning of current competitors and all corresponding emerging trends. Follow-up insights were reported in D7.2 "[Intermediate Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)" and D7.3 "[Business Model Design and Evaluation](#)" as well as a summary in D7.4 "[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)".

3. The analytical definition of all possible commercial and non-commercial exploitation models, which have been preliminarily identified and are outlined in detail in the deliverable D7.2 [“Intermediate Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy”](#) and finalised in D7.4 [“Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy”](#).
4. The analytical definition and evaluation of the sustainability and viability of possible business models and alternative solutions that may be followed for the provision of the project solution and services to the identified stakeholders, including licensing schemes, pricing, etc., are reported in the first Horizon Results Booster Service Report (PDES-Module C final report for TRIPLE project)²⁵.
5. The establishment of relationships of trust with customers/users early within the project, who can facilitate the quicker adoption of the solution and provide valuable feedback which can be used in the commercialisation phase.
6. The identification of financial support from diversified funds (including for example institutional funds or other private and/or public funds) that can be used to support direct and/or indirect commercial transformation, ranging from additional research activities to bug fixing and to technology integration in existing or future solutions. More information on these topics is provided in the Horizon Results Booster Service Report (BPD final report for Triple project²⁶) and D7.4 [“Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy”](#).

Exploitation intensity: The exploitation activities varied in intensity based on the delivery of the project results and the acquisition of research and development (R&D) know-how. Towards this end, the exploitation activities have started mildly with the identification of the innovative exploitable assets of the project and the conduction of a preliminary market analysis identifying potential stakeholders and competitors. Prior to the delivery of the intermediate project results, we intensified our activities with a more analytical definition of all possible commercial and non-commercial exploitation models and a definition and evaluation of the sustainability and viability of possible business models and alternative solutions. The peak of exploitation activities was prior to the delivery of the project’s final results when the project dissemination activities were also intense. The main task was to reach and attract potential stakeholders and customers.

Exploitation objectives: The exploitation strategy of TRIPLE followed three main stages of expansion with specific short-term, medium-term and long-term objectives:

1. **Short-term objectives:** This first stage corresponds to a period beginning with the start of the project activities and ends in parallel with the project. During this period, the main objective was to develop a highly accepted platform (with exceptional usability and user experience) in order to gain a solid data inflow from the

²⁵ PDES stands for Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy service provided by Virag Zsar from the European HRB program. The report is confidential but has been sent to the Project Officer.

²⁶ BPD stands for Business Plan Development service provided by Virag Zsar from the European HRB program. The report is confidential but has been sent to the Project Officer.

- researchers. Furthermore, the TRIPLE results, concepts, models, tools and services were verified and validated.
2. **Medium-term objectives:** This second stage corresponds to a period beginning with the end of the project and ending after two or three years, depending on the maturity and completion of the project results. The main objective includes the commercialisation of the “to date” results and developments of semi-commercial products and services, while it further relates to potential fine-tuning, or expansion of the GoTriple platform and services.
 3. **Long-term objectives:** The last stage corresponds to the commercialisation of the GoTriple platform and services derived from the first and second stages.

3.5. Intellectual Property Rights Management

The knowledge and protection management plan is in the final phase during the preparation of the Consortium Agreement. The purpose of the Consortium Agreement is to establish a legal framework for the project in order to provide clear regulations for issues within the consortium related to IP ownership, confidential information, Open Source issues, standard contributions, and access rights to background and foreground IP for the duration of the project and any other matters of the consortium’s interest. The TRIPLE consortium uses the DESCA 2020 model. Although the Consortium Agreement is a basic and stable document, it will be modified in the course of the project duration to take into account any updated consensus on the project results. The TRIPLE project plans to contribute to the debates and evolutions that are currently taking place in the crucial domain of intellectual property rights and propose new solutions. TRIPLE collects and processes openly available contents, accordingly to their access rights and licensing information. TRIPLE makes the collected metadata about the contents openly available through its platform and APIs, including all the specific access rights and licensing information provided by the data providers.

4. TRIPLE KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KER)

Within this section, an overview of all the KERs that have been developed within the TRIPLE project has been provided (see Figure 8). Although the GoTriple platform is the main KER of the TRIPLE project (KER 1), additional 5 KERs (KER 2-6) are described briefly by providing a short description, a maturity classification and information on sustainability. Furthermore, the final GoTriple Business Model including a summary of the GoTripe Business Plan is presented.

4.1. Overview of TRIPLE KERs

Figure 8 presents all developed TRIPLE KERs which are classified into 4 areas, Data Sets & Management, Processing, Methodologies & Analysis, Training & Support and the TRIPLE innovative Services

FIGURE 8. SCHEMATIC OVERVIEW OF TRIPLE KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS.

KER 1: GoTriple Discovery platform for SSH resources

Description:

GoTriple is a multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities (SSH). Based on the Isidore search engine developed by the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), GoTriple provides a single access point for users (researchers, institutions such as universities and libraries, but also enterprises and the media). It allows users to

- Discover and reuse open scholarly SSH resources in 11 European languages ((Croatian, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Spanish, Polish, Portuguese, Ukrainian and Slovenian), i.e. research data and publications, which are currently scattered across local repositories;
- Find and connect with other researchers and projects across disciplinary and language boundaries;

- Make use of innovative tools to support research (e.g. visualisation, web annotation, trust building and recommender system);
- Discover new ways of funding research through crowdfunding.

The core of the GoTriple platform is mainly a “pipeline” where data are ingested, classified, enriched and categorised so they can be easily found and retrieved by the users. The platform increases the visibility and quality of SSH research through an easier/better SSH-focused research platform. GoTriple facilitates more efficient and effective SSH research for societies at large by involving civil society, public institutions and companies in scientific projects, thus strengthening the links between different types of stakeholders. Non-open access sources are less prominent and get marked as not open access. The current version (February 2023) is available via <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

Maturity: TRL9

Sustainability:

A dedicated governance and business model have been developed (more details in section 3). A Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is available and describes how the individual partners will continue to coordinate and sustain the overall service, along with Operational Level Agreements (OLAs) or Underpinning Agreements (UAs)²⁷ with the individual service component providers to maintain and evolve the technical aspects of the service, which is aimed to be in place prior to the end of the project. The Research Infrastructure OPERAS will lead the partners involved in the platform, support its maintenance, and provide the legal, administrative and organisational sustainability for the service.

KER 2 - Multilingual Vocabulary Service

Description:

The solution is a publicly available SSH vocabulary, published in an open format (e.g. SKOS) - and vocabulary data are downloadable as XML or JSON files. Future possibilities include the development of an API for automatic integration in digital environments to enable dynamic translation and classification. The multilingual vocabulary is already scalable and may be developed further in the future as the classifications expand. As mentioned before, the vocabulary covers 11 different languages by February 2023, but is expandable to other languages (this is relatively easy because the structure already exists and therefore a native speaker can enrich this structure with their language). It can be integrated into various different types of platforms (via json/database file import or more dynamically by using the API that will be developed). The methodology of the classification process is unique: algorithms for automatic classification and translation and human-curated classification and translation.

Maturity: TRL8

Sustainability:

²⁷ OLAs for OPERAS members; UAs for external suppliers

Since the Vocabulary Service is an integrated component of the GoTriple platform economic sustainability is associated with the GoTriple business plan considerations. Nevertheless, a separate exploitation in the context of the first Horizon Results Booster Module PDES²⁸ has also been considered. Suitable target markets identified customer segments and designed a draft Business Model that covers defined roles, cost estimations and potential revenue streams were researched. The vocabulary containing 11 languages as of February 2023 can be expanded. This work is very valuable in order to increase the impact and foster the reuse of research for the SSH communities worldwide. More information regarding sustainability can be found in D7.4 [“Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy”](#) section 2.2.

KER 3: SSH corpus for Machine Learning Training

Description:

Constitution of a training textual dataset of SSH sources that can be reused for training machine learning and artificial intelligence tasks. This corpus covers each of the 27 SSH disciplines identified in TRIPLE. It is a multilingual set covering the aforementioned 11 European languages. This corpus currently comprises more than 250,000 documents and has been tested in production for the implementation of the automatic classification service in GoTriple.

Maturity: TRL8.

Sustainability:

Similar to the previous KER 2 the sustainability aspects of the SSH corpus for Machine Learning Training need to be addressed in the context of the GoTriple business plan. The costs incurred for maintaining the service and necessary updates were taken into account in the general cost assessment for the GoTriple platform (see D7.4 [“Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy”](#) section 3.4). In case of an expansion e.g. adding a new language cause high effort to train the databases for each discipline. The decision on such an extension and how the expenditure could be covered will be taken by the GoTriple Committee.

KER 4: FAIR Metadata schema

Description:

The FAIR Metadata schema is a reference data model for describing research documents, projects, authors, and research profiles of the SSH community and beyond. It is based on a standard and well-known ontology such as schema.org. It provides links with the TRIPLE vocabulary concepts. Before the end of the project in March 2023, it will be formally described through a machine-readable standard ontology, paving the way to publish GoTriple data (and possibly all services reusing it) as linked data.

Maturity: TRL8.

²⁸ PDES stands for Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy provided by Virag Zsar from the European HRB program. The resulting final report is confidential but has been sent to the Project Officer.

Sustainability:

The sustainability aspect (maintenance and required updates) of this KER is covered by the general GoTriple business plan (see D7.4 “[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)” section 3).

KER 5: TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

Description:

A series of 12 online training events on Open Science and the EOSC to support the uptake of open research practices. The training and the related materials are made available in Open Access to the SSH community (on Zenodo).

Maturity: TRL8

Sustainability:

All training material is available via, the [TRIPLE project website](#), [Zenodo](#) and [DARIAH-Campus](#) ensuring their long-term availability. The GoTriple Committee will monitor its usage and continue to disseminate and communicate them. No additional costs are foreseen. Additional information can be found in D7.4 “[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)” section 2.3.2

KER 6: TRIPLE Training Toolkit

Description:

The TRIPLE Training Toolkit is an open and reusable workflow to design and deliver training events that follow the FAIR principles and to publish training materials as OERs. It contains reproducible files to help trainers minimise the time they spend in the design and delivery of FAIR training events and supports them in addressing the frequent findability and reusability issues related to the management of digital training resources. To facilitate the uptake of the FAIR-by-design method, the Toolkit comes with a step-by-step illustration of the user journey.

Maturity: TRL8

Sustainability:

In general this KER is finalised and no further costs are envisioned. Within the projects’ exploitation activities early adopters and specified customer segments for the KER were identified. The Toolkit is available under a CC license via [Zenodo](#). More details can be found in D7.4 “[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)” section 2.3.1.

4.2. GoTriple Business Model

One of the main objectives of WP7 activities was to make sure that the main Key Exploitable Result of the TRIPLE project, the GoTriple discovery platform, is economically sustainable after the project ends. To ensure this, the development of a suitable business model (BM) is essential. Many activities in WP7, but also in all other WPs, have contributed to the development of the GoTriple Business Model. Before outlining the status of the GoTriple Business Model a brief overview of the actual state of the GoTriple platform is provided.

In February 2023, about 5.100.000 documents (publications and datasets) have been retrieved via a pipeline where data are ingested, classified, enriched, and categorised so that users can easily find and retrieve them. The following aggregators and data providers are progressively imported into the platform: DOAJ, EKT, Isidore (which includes DOAB and OAPEN), OpenAIRE, Biblioteka Nauki, CESSDA, ZRC-SAZU, COIMBRA, Open Edition, Clarin, Econstor and BASE. Both aggregators and providers cover the 11 languages of GoTriple (see section 4.1 above). 27 SSH disciplines are also covered in each of the languages.

GoTriple allows multilingual search, which means that users can find publications in a specific language by using keywords in one of the languages supported by the platform. A TRIPLE thesaurus is integrated into the platform containing exactly 3375 concepts available in all languages. Documents are annotated with the concepts of the TRIPLE thesaurus on the page of each document.

The search engine allows different filters such as publication type, author, year and discipline. The right side of the Figure 9 shows the results for “french art history” authors. The number of publications per author containing this concept is indicated in front of each author. Clicking on the number of publications per author gives access to the details of the publications.

FIGURE 9. SCREENSHOT OF THE GOTRIPLE MAIN PAGE AND SEARCH RESULTS (SCREENSHOT TAKEN IN FEBRUARY 2023)

Based on the initial BM designs outlined in D7.1 “[Report on Stakeholder- and Opportunity Analysis](#)” and D7.2 “[Intermediate Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)” we constantly further developed the GoTriple BM conducted by the WP7 project team and supported by the entire TRIPLE partners. The main focus was on improving the Value Proposition including the development of suitable Membership Bundles, getting more information on the targeted customer groups and getting a clear picture of the BM viability aspects in terms of potential revenue streams and cost estimations. In the following, the updated GoTriple BMs are divided into the 2 most important customer groups (Researchers, Institutions) and presented in form of the Business Model Canvas by Osterwalder & Pigneur²⁹.

GoTriple Unique Value Proposition:

GoTRIPLE improves the access to open content and resources of social sciences and humanities (SSH) research and facilitates collaborations across disciplinary and language boundaries through innovative services like annotations, a trust building system, new visualizations (knowledge maps, stream graphs) and crowdfunding possibilities. GoTRIPLE will be connected to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and integrated into OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities).

GoTriple’s USP can be summarized as:

- offering multilingualism,
- creation of links and connections to different data sources,
- bridging of disciplines,
- offering integrated service and
- offering crowdfunding.

No other platform is covering the combination of features that GoTriple offers and additionally focuses on SSH explicitly, thus it is assumed that the GoTriple platform could bring added value to the open science landscape.

BM aspects for Customer Segment “Researcher”

Value Proposition:

- Easy exploration of SSH research outputs
- Findability of resources across language barriers
- Connectivity with SSH researchers, and possibility for collaboration
- Funding one’s SSH research project

Targeted Customer Groups:

²⁹ Osterwalder, Alexander & Pigneur, Yves (2010). *Business Model Generation. A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.

- SSH researchers (students, PhD students, junior and senior academics)
- Non-SSH researchers (Businesses, NGO's, Policy Makers)
- Identified early adopters: Researchers from academic partners of TRIPLE consortium

Revenue Streams:

- Micro Donations from users
- In-kind contribution from TRIPLE consortium partners
- OPERAS AISBL contribution for sustaining the core service components of GoTriple

BM Aspects for Customer Segment “Institutions”

Value Proposition:

- Make SSH research visible to the world (directing to the Sustaining Membership service bundle)
- Shape the future of exploring SSH research (directing to the Visionary Membership service bundle)

Targeted Customer Groups:

- SSH research focused institutions in Europe
 - EU focused Universities (about 280)
 - Private research centres (e.g. Max Plank Institute)
- Libraries
- Government-type institutions (e.g. statistical bureaus)

Revenue Streams:

- Membership Fees (Sustaining and Visionary Membership)
- Institutional one-time donations
- In-kind contribution from TRIPLE consortium partners (organised in GoTriple Committee see section 3.1)
- OPERAS AISBL contribution for sustaining the core service components of GoTriple

FIGURE 10. FINAL GoTRIPLE BUSINESS MODEL

GoTriple Business Plan

A comprehensive document that outlines the strategies, the organisational structure (governance model), market analysis, and financial projections, etc constitutes a business plan for GoTriple. It should act as a roadmap for the operation and growth of the GoTriple platform and should be used to secure funding, attract new partners, and make informed decisions. The business plan includes details on GoTriple's offerings, target market, competition, governance model, operations, and financial projections. The GoTriple business plan is seen as a tool for tracking progress, making adjustments, and ensuring the long-term success of the business. A detailed roadmap (schedule of specific activities) for the first year after the completion of the project is being developed in February 2023.

The following milestones for the first year after the project ends are currently defined as:

- M1 Constitution of the GoTriple Committee (chair/vice chair elected, OPERAS STB representative defined, all needed roles assigned) at the end of M1 (April 2023)
- M2 All contracts with service component providers signed → M2
- M3 User Survey Results available → M6
- M4 Financial sustainability secured (costs are covered by revenues) → M12

A detailed description of the business plan can be found in D7.4 "[Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy](#)".

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This deliverable summarised those activities of the TRIPLE project's consortium dedicated to ensuring sustainable dissemination and exploitation of the project's results. In section 1 of the deliverable, we gave an overview of the TRIPLE project, featuring key facts and figures as well as the goals and impacts aimed for.

Section 2 put focus on the dissemination of results, describing the dissemination measures taken and the UES that has conceptually influenced the dissemination activity throughout RP 3. With GoTriple being in the later stages of production, dissemination activities revolved mainly around engaging users. Measures that have been taken include but are not limited to ambassadorships, collaborations, outreach events, workshops, trainings and the creation of sustainable information material representing the platform's multilingual and multifaceted design. Furthermore, this section explored how dissemination activities will be kept up after the project has ended in March 2023. As the discovery service GoTriple is part of the OPERAS service portfolio and will be operated by OPERAS from April 2023 on, OPERAS is an integral part of the project's long-term dissemination strategy with visual material, fact sheets and a brochure featuring TRIPLE's KERs being created for dissemination via OPERAS and the RIs national nodes.

Section 3 concentrated on the exploitation strategy of the TRIPLE project, featuring the results of the joint exploitation survey and the alignment with the OPERAS exploitation strategy to guarantee a smooth transfer and maximum efficiency.

Finally, the deliverable featured an overview of the project's 6 KERs and the GoTriple business model in section 4. Pointing out how the project's results are contributing to the European Open Science landscape already, the description of the KERs also highlighted how the business model the team of WP7 designed in collaboration with OPERAS aims for the economic sustainability of the GoTriple platform.

In conclusion, the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project in the last reporting period (from February 2022 to March 2023) focused on three main goals: 1) to recruit users for the GoTriple discovery service, 2) to build the foundation for sustainable dissemination measures that outlive the project's funding period, 3) to create a business model that ensures maximal possible exploitation of and sustainability for the project's results.